

Financial Performance and Socioeconomic Characteristics of Rice Farmers under Government Credit Intervention Schemes in South-East Nigeria, 1999 – 2024

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Abstract: This study investigated the financial performance and socioeconomic characteristics of rice farmers under government credit intervention schemes in South-East Nigeria between 1999 and 2024. The research aimed to examine the socioeconomic attributes of rice farmers (beneficiaries and non-beneficiaries) in the study area and to evaluate the financial performance of the schemes among beneficiaries. A multi-stage sampling procedure, incorporating purposive, random, and proportionate techniques, was employed to select 543 rice farmers, comprising 264 beneficiaries and 279 non-beneficiaries, whose data was further obtained using a structured questionnaire. Data were analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistical methods. Results indicated that the mean ages of beneficiaries and non-beneficiaries were 40.7 years and 45.1 years, respectively, with mean farm sizes of 1.73 hectares and 1.14 hectares. Mean farming experience was 19.3 years for beneficiaries, 20.6 years for non-beneficiaries, and 19.9 years overall, while the average household size was 7 persons. Financial performance analysis revealed that farmers demanded a mean credit amount of ₦516,757.58 but received ₦328,670.45, reflecting a 36.50% shortfall. The Z-test ($Z = 4.17$; $p < 0.01$) confirmed significant underfunding. The study concluded that the credit provided was inadequate relative to production requirements and recommended increased credit volumes alongside improved timeliness of disbursement. These findings contribute to the broader discourse on agricultural financing in developing economies, highlighting the persistent gap between policy intentions and farmers' production realities.

Keywords: Rice Farmers, Agricultural credit, financial performance, Intervention schemes, South-East Nigeria, Credit Gap

1.0 Introduction

Agriculture has been the backbone of Nigeria's economy, sustaining livelihoods and driving national development even before the discovery of crude oil. It contributes over 25% to Nigeria's GDP, and the sector plays a major role in employment creation. The National Bureau of Statistics (2017) and Trading Economics (2025) show that agriculture engaged about 48% of the workforce in 2006, dropping gradually to 27% in 2015, yet rising again to 34.31% in 2023 according to ILO estimates. Despite this importance, access to finance for agricultural production remains critically low. The World Bank (2020) reports that although agriculture employs roughly 55% of Africa's population, only about 1% of bank lending goes to the sector, while merely 4.7% of rural adults in developing countries hold loans from formal institutions. Nigeria reflects the same pattern: with nearly 218.5 million people, about half living in rural areas, and one of the world's largest unemployed youth populations (IBRD, 2022), the agricultural sector remains financially underserved.

Smallholder farmers face a range of persistent constraints: poor infrastructure, low productivity, and limited access to

markets, inadequate risk-management tools, and, most critically, poor access to credit. As Yahaya & Osemene (2011) noted, revitalizing agriculture relies heavily on empowering farmers and expanding their access to production resources, particularly credit. Years of public neglect further deepened the sector's decline, leaving Nigeria heavily dependent on food imports, despite its historical leadership in palm oil, cocoa, groundnuts, and other export crops. The FBN 2013 Investment Research Report highlights this irony: Malaysia, which once sourced oil palm seedlings from Nigeria, now earns more from palm oil than Nigeria earns from crude petroleum.

After the return to democratic rule in 1999, successive governments have repeatedly attempted to reposition agriculture as the mainstay of the country's economy. Yet, the sector continues to show neglect in terms of financing. Oxfam (2011–2015) describes Nigeria as “a rich nation of poor people,” endowed with vast arable land yet unable to feed itself. Despite numerous agricultural policies, OFN, Green Revolution, DFFRI, ADP, RBDAs, and NAFPP to reposition the sector, poor implementation and inconsistency remain major challenge. Ejukonemu & Akintola (2013) attribute this

to top-down decision-making that excludes intended beneficiaries, making farmers passive observers in programmes designed for their upliftment.

Recognizing the centrality of credit, Nigeria's agricultural policy framework emphasizes sustainable financing schemes to support producers, processors, and marketers. Government interventions such as the Commercial Agriculture Credit Scheme (CACCS), Agricultural Credit Support Scheme (ACSS), and Anchor Borrowers' Programme (ABP) were created to close financing gaps. Yet smallholder farmers in Nigeria still experience inadequate access to formal credit.

Several scholars have investigated agricultural finance, but their studies vary widely in focus and leave critical gaps unexplored. Agbada (2015) assessed the adequacy of public funding for agriculture, while Agunuwa, Inaya & Proso (2015) examined broad determinants of agricultural financing, yet both studies failed to evaluate farmer-level performance resulting from specific credit schemes. Nwankwo (2013) analysed the Agricultural Credit Guarantee Scheme (ACGS), but did not compare productivity outcomes of beneficiaries versus non-beneficiaries. Udoka & Duke (2016) highlighted the general challenges of

agricultural financing without assessing the real impacts of intervention schemes on farmers' livelihoods. Okoh (2015) focused on government expenditure on agriculture, offering macro-level insights that do not reveal whether credit interventions actually improve farmer performance. Likewise, international studies (Asiedu et al., 2013; Awotide et al., 2015; Abid and Gopal, 2015; Ali & Awade, 2019) addressed systemic credit constraints but did not evaluate Nigerian rice farmers or compare credit beneficiaries with non-beneficiaries.

Across these studies, a clear gap exists: none considered the financial performance and socioeconomic characteristics of rice farmers in Nigeria, and no study links farmer-level socioeconomic characteristics, credit access and performance outcomes within the context of the major financing schemes implemented between 1999 and 2024. Therefore, this study tried to fill this crucial gap, and in addressing the gap, the study aimed at analysing the socioeconomic characteristics of the rice farmers (beneficiaries and non-beneficiaries) in the study area, and assessing the financial performance of government agricultural credit intervention schemes for the beneficiary rice farmers.

2.0 Materials and Methods

The study was carried out in South-East Nigeria, comprising Abia, Anambra, Ebonyi, Enugu, and Imo States. The region lies between latitudes 4°10'–7°08'N and longitudes 5°30'–9°27'E, with a population of 16.3 million people (National Population Commission, NPC, 2006) and estimated population of 29 million (NPC, 2024). It falls within the rainforest ecological zone and covers about 10.95 million hectares. The climate is humid, with annual rainfall of 2000–3000 mm, mean temperature of 28°C, and two marked seasons, rainy (March–October) and dry (November–February). Farming is a major occupation in the zone, with rice, yam, cassava, maize, and cocoyam as dominant food crops, and cocoa, palm oil, rubber, and cotton as cash crops (Okoye et al., 2010; Osuji et al., 2012). The region was selected because it is a major beneficiary of government agricultural financing schemes and is a key rice-producing hub supported by programmes such as CADP (NBS, 2019).

A multi-stage sampling design, combining purposive, random, and proportionate techniques was adopted to select rice farmers for the study. In the first stage, three States with the highest rice output and the largest concentration of beneficiaries of

agricultural financing schemes were purposively chosen: Anambra, Ebonyi, and Enugu (NBS, 2019). In the second stage, one Local Government Area (LGA) was purposively selected from each agricultural zone in the three States, giving a total of nine LGAs. These LGAs were chosen based on their strong involvement in rice production. The third stage involved the purposive selection of six rice-producing communities from each of the nine LGAs, resulting in 54 communities across the States. In the fourth stage, sampling frames of registered rice farmers were used to stratify farmers into beneficiaries and non-beneficiaries of agricultural financing schemes. These sampling frames were compiled with the assistance of ADP officials, resident extension agents, and RIFAN leaders. The Taro Yamane (1967) formula, also applied in Ohajianya et al. (2016) & Nwaiwu (2014), was then used to determine the appropriate sample sizes at a 5% precision level:

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e^2)} \quad (1)$$

Using this formula produced sample sizes of 264 beneficiaries and 279 non-beneficiaries.

From the stratified lists, a proportionate random sampling technique was applied to account for the unequal population sizes across States. This yielded 95 beneficiaries from Ebonyi, 91 from Enugu, and 78 from Anambra. For non-beneficiaries, 101 were selected from Ebonyi, 93 from Enugu, and 85 from Anambra. Altogether, this resulted in a total sample size of 543 respondents.

The non-beneficiaries were included solely to provide additional descriptive information on the socioeconomic characteristics of rice farmers in the study area.

2.1 Model Specification

Descriptive statistics such as frequencies, percentages, and means were used to summarize the socio-economic characteristics of the respondents. Inferential statistics, specifically the z-test, were employed to compare the level of agricultural interventions received by

farmers with the level of interventions they demanded.

The Z-test model as used by Ohajianya *et al.* (2016) and Nwaiwu (2014) was adopted for this study and specified as follows:

$$Z_{cal} = \frac{\bar{x}_1 - \bar{x}_2}{\sqrt{\frac{S_1^2}{n_1} + \frac{S_2^2}{n_2}}} \quad (2)$$

where:

Z = the Z-statistic

\bar{x}_1 = mean amount of intervention received by farmers

\bar{x}_2 = mean amount of intervention demanded by farmers

S_1 = variance of the intervention received by farmers

S_2 = variance of intervention demanded by farmers

n_1 = sample size of farmers who received the intervention

$$n_2 = n_1$$

3.0 Results and Discussion

Socioeconomic Characteristics of the Rice Farmers

The socioeconomic characteristics of rice farmers (beneficiaries and non-beneficiaries) of the government intervention programmes are presented in Table 1.

Table 1 presents the socioeconomic characteristics of both beneficiary and non-beneficiary rice farmers in the agricultural financing scheme in South-East Nigeria. The results show that 70.6% of non-beneficiaries fall within the 39–58 years age bracket, compared to 51.9% of beneficiaries and 61.5% of the pooled sample. The mean ages were 45.1 years (non-beneficiaries), 40.7 years (beneficiaries), and 42.9 years (pooled). These mean values indicate that farmers in both groups are within their economically active years, but beneficiaries appear slightly younger. This pattern

suggests that government agricultural financing schemes are attracting and engaging younger farmers. The result is consistent with FAO (2019) and Obiora et al. (2024), who found that younger farmers (31–40 years) are central to driving agricultural growth when properly supported. The trend in this study shows that recent financing interventions are contributing to increased youth participation in rice farming, enhancing the long-term sustainability of rice production in the region.

The results further show average farming experience of 20.6 years (non-beneficiaries), 19.3 years (beneficiaries), and 19.9 years (pooled). Although both groups are highly experienced, beneficiaries have slightly fewer years of experience, likely due to the period when the financing schemes were introduced. This suggests that the schemes did not target only inexperienced farmers; instead, they involved both new and

seasoned farmers. The finding contrasts with Kafayat et al. (2023), who reported farming experience of 6–10 years among rice farmers, but aligns with Onoja et al. (2024), who found that farming experience significantly influenced rice yield among beneficiaries. The inclusion of relatively newer farmers may also reflect an intentional effort to bring younger or less-experienced individuals into rice production to boost food security.

Table 1 also reveals mean farm sizes of 1.14 ha (non-beneficiaries), 1.73 ha (beneficiaries), and 1.44 ha (pooled). This indicates that beneficiaries operated larger farm sizes than non-beneficiaries, even though both groups remain smallholders. Access to financing likely enabled beneficiaries to lease, acquire, or optimize more land. Larger farm sizes generally enhance production potential, support economies of scale, and improve income, all factors that strengthen farmer performance.

This aligns with Onwuemene et al. (2024), who reported that agricultural financing programs such as the Agricultural Credit Guarantee Scheme exert significant positive effects on agricultural sector performance.

Furthermore, Table 1 shows a notable difference in household size distribution. Among households with 1–5 members, 40.2% of beneficiaries fall into this category compared to 34.4% of non-beneficiaries. The mean household size across groups was seven persons. Larger households provide readily available family labour, which is particularly important for labour-intensive rice production in the region. This result is consistent with Onoja et al. (2024), who reported that household size significantly influenced rice yield among financing scheme beneficiaries.

Table 1: Socioeconomic characteristics of rice farmers in the South East Nigeria

Variables	Non-Beneficiaries (n = 279)		Beneficiaries (n = 264)		Pooled Sample (n = 543)	
	Frequency	Percentage (%)	Frequency	Percentage (%)	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Age (Year)						
19 - 38 years	64	22.9	113	42.8	177	32.6
39 - 58 years	197	70.6	137	51.9	334	61.5
59 years and above	18	6.5	14	5.3	32	5.9
Mean Age		45.1 Years		40.7 Years		42.9 Years
Farming experience (Year)						
1 - 5 years	0	0.0	28	10.6	28	5.2
6 - 10 years	50	17.9	44	16.7	94	17.3
11 - 15 years	74	26.5	49	18.6	123	22.7
16 years and above	155	55.6	143	54.1	298	54.8
Mean Farm Experience		20.6 Years		19.3 Years		19.9 Years
Farm size (Hectare)						
0.00 - 0.50 ha	19	6.8	19	7.2	38	7.0
0.51 - 1.00 ha	190	68.1	175	66.3	365	67.2
1.10 - 1.50 ha	35	12.5	35	13.3	70	12.9
1.51 - 2.00 ha	25	9.0	25	9.5	50	9.2
2.10 ha and above	10	3.6	10	3.8	20	3.7
Mean Farm Size		1.14 Hectares		1.73 Hectares		1.44 Hectares
Household size (Number of Persons)						
1 – 5	96	34.4	106	40.2	202	37.2
6 – 10	166	59.5	112	42.4	278	51.2
11 – 15	14	5	34	12.9	48	8.8
16 and above	3	1.1	12	4.5	15	2.8
Mean Household size		7 Persons		7 Persons		7 Persons

Source: Computed from Field Survey Data, 2025.

Assessment of the Financial Performance of Government Agricultural Credit Intervention Schemes

Table 2 presents the result of the assessment of the financial performance of government agricultural credit intervention Schemes by rice farmers in South-East Nigeria.

Table 2: Financial Performance of Government Agricultural Credit Intervention Schemes

Credit Category	Frequency	Percentage (%)	Mean (₦)	Min (₦)	Max (₦)
A. Amount demanded (₦)			516,757.58	20,000	999,000
10,000 - 99,999	26	9.8			
100,000 - 199,999	22	8.3			
200,000 - 299,999	24	9.1			
300,000 - 399,999	27	10.2			
400,000 and above	165	62.5			
B. Amount Received (₦)			328,670.45	8,000	816,000
1,000 - 99,999	45	17			
100,000 - 199,999	39	14.8			
200,000 - 299,999	34	12.9			
300,000 - 399,999	61	23.1			
400,000 and above	85	32.2			
Performance Measure					
Percentage Received			63.60%		
Percentage difference			36.50%		
Z-value			4.17***		

Significance at 1% (***) level of probability

Source: Computed from Field Survey Data, 2025

The performance of the government agricultural credit intervention schemes was evaluated by comparing the amount of financial credit demanded by beneficiary

rice farmers with the actual amount of credit received. The findings indicate a substantial performance gap in the delivery of credit to the intended beneficiaries.

The results show that beneficiary rice farmers demanded a mean credit amount of ₦516,757.58 and received only a mean amount of ₦328,670.45. This represents 63.60% of the total amount demanded, leaving a shortfall of 36.50%, which underscores a significant underperformance of the credit delivery system. This aligns with the World Bank (2021), which reported that although agriculture engages about 55% of Africa's population, it still receives only about 1% of total bank lending.

The statistical test provides further evidence of performance gaps. The Z-value of 4.17 ($p < 0.01$) confirms a highly significant difference between the amount demanded and the amount received by beneficiary farmers. In total, these results show that the government credit intervention schemes reached the intended beneficiaries; they did not sufficiently meet the actual financing needs of rice farmers. The underfunding of credit requests reduces farmers' ability to expand production, purchase improved inputs, and invest in technologies that enhance productivity.

Finally, the financial performance of the intervention schemes can be classified as moderate but insufficient, with clear evidence of credit inadequacy and

suboptimal delivery relative to farmers' real financial requirements. The results affirm the earlier findings of Udoka & Duke (2016) and Okoh (2015), who reported that government efforts to transform the agricultural sector through financing have not achieved the desired impact due to persistent funding inadequacies.

4.0 Conclusion

The study concluded that rice farmers in South-East Nigeria are predominantly within their economically active years, with beneficiaries of government agricultural financing interventions slightly younger than non-beneficiaries. Beneficiaries also operated larger farms, suggesting that access to credit may have facilitated expansion in farm size.

The study also concluded that despite these positive effects, there exists a significant gap between the amount of financial credit demanded and what was actually received. This limits farmers' ability to invest in modern inputs, scale production, and enhance productivity.

Finally, the study concluded that while government agricultural financing interventions reached rice farmers and have

some positive impact, structural inefficiencies in disbursement undermine

their full potential to improve farm performance and livelihoods.

References

- Abid, M., & Gopal, R. (2015). Agricultural Credit and Economic Growth Nexus: Evidence from Pakistan. *Pakistan Journal of Agricultural Sciences*, 52(3), 857–864.
- Agbada, A.O. (2015). Agricultural Financing and Optimising Output for Sustainable Economic Development in Nigeria: An Empirical Analysis. *Journal of Emerging Trends in Economics and Management Sciences (JETEMS)*, Vol. 6(5), pp. 359–366.
- Agunuwa, E.V., Inaya, L., & Proso, T. (2015). Impact of Commercial Banks' Credit on Agricultural Productivity in Nigeria (Time Series Analysis 1980–2013). *International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social Sciences*, 5(11), 337–350.
- Ali, E., & Awade, N.E. (2019). Credit Constraints and Soybean Farmers' Welfare in Subsistence Agriculture in Togo. *Heliyon*, 5(5), e01550. DOI: 10.1016/j.heliyon.2019.e01550
- Asiedu, E., Kalonda-Kanyama, I., Ndikumana, L., & Nti-Addae, A. (2013). Access to Credit by Firms in Sub-Saharan Africa: How Relevant is Gender? *African Development Review*, 25(4), 400–420.
- Awotide, B.A., Abdoulaye, T., Alene, A., & Manyong, V.M. (2015). Impact of Access to Credit on Agricultural Productivity: Evidence from Smallholder Rice Farmers in Nigeria. Conference Paper, International Association of Agricultural Economists (IAAE), Milan, Italy.
- Ejuronemu, F., & Akintola, J.O. (2013). Agricultural productivity and socioeconomic characteristics of farmers in Nigeria. *Journal of Agricultural Economics and Rural Development*, Vol. 1(1), pp. 61–77.

- Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO). (2019). Rural Development Report 2019: Creating Opportunities for Rural Youth. Rome: FAO.
- International Bank for Reconstruction and Development (IBRD)/World Bank. (2022). Population, total Nigeria. World Development Indicators. Retrieved from <https://data.worldbank.org/indicator/SP.POP.TOTL?locations=NG>
- Kafayat, A., Idoma, K., Musa, I. T., & Amina, S. S. (2023). Assessment of the socioeconomic characteristics and constraints of rice farmers in Yamaltu-Deba LGA, Gombe State, Nigeria. In Book of Proceedings of the 1st North-East Conference of the Association of Nigerian Geographers (ANG), Department of Geography, Gombe State University.
- National Bureau of Statistics (2017). Nigeria Poverty Assessment. NBS in collaboration with World Bank and DFID :38 - 185.
- NBS (2019). Poverty and Inequality in Nigeria: Executive Summary. Abuja: National Bureau of Statistics.
- NPC (2006). Population and Housing Census of the Federal Republic of Nigeria: Priority Tables (Vol. I). Abuja: National Population Commission
- NPC (2024). Nigeria Demographic and Health Survey (NDHS) 2023–24: Key Indicators Report. Abuja: National Population Commission, Federal Ministry of Health, and The DHS Program
- Nwaiwu, I.U. (2014). Impact of Agricultural Financing on Economic Growth in Nigeria (1980–2014). Unpublished MSc Thesis, Federal University of Technology Owerri.
- Nwankwo, O. (2013). Agricultural Financing in Nigeria: An Empirical Study of Nigerian Agricultural Co-operative and Rural Development Bank (NACRDB), Enugu. International Journal of Research in Social Sciences, Vol. 3(2), pp. 17–25.

- Obiora, C. C., Anene, K. N., & Ohanu, V. C. (2024). *Socio-economic characteristics of rice farmers in Nigeria*. UNIZIK Journal of Educational Research and Policy Studies, 17(3), 128-136.
- Ohajianya, D.O., et al. (2016). Impact of Agricultural Financing on Agricultural Output in Nigeria: An Empirical Analysis. *Journal of Agriculture and Environment*, Vol. 13(1), pp. 13–26.
- Okoh, J.A. (2015). Agricultural Financing and Economic Development in Nigeria (1986–2015): A Disaggregate Analysis. *Novelty Journals – International Journal of Innovative Finance and Economics Research*, Vol. 3(2), pp. 45–58.
- Okoye, L.U., Evbuomwan, G.O., & Uchenna, A. (2010). *Agricultural Value Chain Financing and Small Scale Farmers in Nigeria: The Prerequisites*. Covenant University Working Paper
- Onoja, N.M., Olajide, R.B., Haruna, O.E., Ajibade, Y.E. & Onoja, A.E. (2024). Effect of Anchor Borrowers' Programme on rice yield in North-Central, Nigeria. *Journal of Agricultural Extension*, 28(3), 70-78
- Onwuemene, J. L., Ezechi, C. P. D., & Adegun, E. A. (2024). Agricultural sector financing and agricultural sector performance in Nigeria. *Journal of Accounting and Financial Management*, 10(12), 51–65.
- Osuji, C., Mbutor, O.M., Ochu, R.E., & Okafor, I.I. (2012). The Contribution of Finance to Agricultural Production in Nigeria. *Central Bank of Nigeria Economic and Financial Review*, Vol. 51(2), pp. 45–67
- Trading Economics. (2025). *Nigeria — Employment in agriculture (% of total employment)*. Retrieved on 16th August 2022, from <https://tradingeconomics.com/nigeria/employment-in-agriculture-percent-of-total-employment-wb-data.htm>
- Udoka, C.O., Mbat, D.O., & Duke, S.B. (2016). The Effect of Commercial Banks' Credit on Agricultural Production in Nigeria. *Journal of Finance and Accounting*, 4(1), 1–10.

World Bank, 2020. Scaling up Action for Transformative Change: Food Systems 2030. Washington, DC, the World Bank. <https://thedocs.worldbank.org/en/doc/1832116044186205330090022020/original/BrochureFS20306Oct2020.pdf>

Yahaya K, Osemene O (2011). Effectiveness of microfinance banks in alleviating poverty in Kwara State Nigeria. *Global Journal of Management and Business Research* 11:4.

Yamane, T. (1967). *Statistics: An Introductory Analysis* (2nd ed.). New York: Harper and Row.